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1. Бекчанов Алишер Илхамбоевич “НОРМАТИВ-ҲУҚУҚИЙ ҲУЖЖАТ” ТУШУНЧАСИ: ИЛМИЙ ВА ҲУҚУҚИЙ МАЗМУНИ.....	5
2. Нариманов Бекзод Абдувалиевич НОДАВЛАТ НОТИЖОРАТ ТАШКИЛОТЛАРИ МАЪМУРИЙ ҲУҚУҚ СУБЪЕКТИ СИФАТИДА: ДАВЛАТ РЎЙХАТИДАН ЎТКАЗИШНИНГ АЙРИМ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.....	13
3. Алимарданова Ирода Воҳид кизи БИЗНЕС-ОМБУДСМАН: ЖАҲОН ТАЖРИБАСИ ВА УНИНГ ИСТИҚБОЛИ.....	22
4. Қазақбаев Туулбай Керимбаевич КОРПОРАТИВ ШАРТНОМА ТАРАФЛАРИ ВА УЛАРНИНГ ҲУҚУҚ ВА МАЖБУРИЯТЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ.....	29
5. Пўлатов Алишер Рамазанович ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА КРИПТОВАЛЮТАНИ ФУҚАРОЛИК ҲУҚУҚЛАРИ ОБЪЕКТЛАРИНИНГ ТИЗИМИДА ТУТГАН ЎРНИ.....	37
6. Саидова Нигора Акмалевна ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОНЛАЙН-УРЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ СПОРОВ В ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ КОММЕРЦИИ.....	45
7. Fazilov Farkhod Maratovich RECEIVING GIFTS AS A MEANS OF LAUNDERING CRIMINAL PROCEEDS.....	53
8. Nosirov Barkhayot Murodjonovich CYBER SECURITY: IMPORTANCE, DEFINITION, TERMINOLOGICAL AND CONTENT DIFFERENCES.....	61
9. Тошпулатов Акром Икромович ЖИНОЯТ ҲУҚУҚИ ВАЗИФА ВА ФУНКЦИЯЛАРИНИНГ ЖИНОЯТ-ҲУҚУҚИЙ ПРИНЦИПЛАР ШАКЛЛАНИШИДАГИ ЎРНИ.....	66
10. Муҳаммадиев Сарвар Асқар ўғли ЖИНОЯТ ПРОЦЕССИГА ОИД НОРМАТИВ ХУСУСИЯТГА ЭГА ҲУЖЖАТЛАРНИ ТИЗИМЛАШТИРИШДА ЗАМОНАВИЙ АХБОРОТ-ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ИМКОНИАТЛАРИНИ ҚЎЛЛАШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.....	77
11. Хамдамова Фируза Уразалиевна ВОПРОСЫ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЙ ПРАВОСУБЪЕКТНОСТИ ТРАНСНАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ КОРПОРАЦИЙ В ЦИФРОВУЮ ЭРУ И УКРЕПЛЕНИЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОСТИ.....	88
12. Амонов Феруз Салимович КОРРУПЦИЯГА ҚАРШИ КУРАШИШДА ЖАМОАТЧИЛИК НАЗОРАТИНИ АМАЛГА ОШИРИШ МЕХАНИЗМЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ.....	95

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RECEIVING GIFTS AS A MEANS OF LAUNDERING CRIMINAL PROCEEDS

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ANNOTATION

The article analyzes the general concept of money laundering. All over the world, the international community, including the United Nations, recognizes the legalization of proceeds from crime as one of the most widespread and dangerous transnational crimes. The growing danger of the legalization of criminal proceeds in the modern world is of concern to the vast majority of countries in the world community. According to experts, “in recent years, the proceeds from various kinds of crimes in the field of money laundering have been from 2 to 5% of the total world gross product, that is, from 1 to 3 trillion US dollars”. With the globalization of the world financial system, the question arises of the need to coordinate the efforts of states to combat money laundering at the international level. In the world, special importance is attached to the fight against crime, the imposition of sentences by the courts for crimes committed in accordance with the principle of justice, and the liberalization of criminal legislation. Thus, special attention is paid to conducting research in the field of determining responsibility for the legalization of proceeds from crime and preventing the causes and conditions that contribute to its occurrence, the correct qualification of this crime, and strengthening the implementation of international standards in this area in national legislation.

Keywords: crime, criminal liability, proceeds of crime, money laundering, legalization, punishment

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SOVG'ALARNI OLISH JINOIY DAROMADLARNI YUVISH USULI SIFATIDA

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada jinoiy faoliyatdan olingan daromadlarni legallashtirishning umumiy tushunchasi tahlil qilingan. Dunyoda xalqaro hamjamiyat, shu jumladan, Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti tomonidan jinoiy daromadlarni legallashtirish eng keng tarqalgan va xavfli transmilliy jinoyatlardan biridir deb topilgan. Zamonaviy dunyoda jinoiy yoʻl bilan topilgan daromadlarni legallashtirishda ortib borayotgan jamoat xavfi dunyo hamjamiyatini tashvishga solmoqda. Mutaxassislarining fikriga koʻra, “soʻnggi yillarda jinoiy daromadlarni legallashtirish bilan bogʻliq turli xil jinoyatlardan keladigan daromadlar global yalpi mahsulotning 2–5 foizi, yaʼni 1–3 trillion AQSh dollarini tashkil etadi”. Jahon moliyaviy tizimining globallashuvi sharoitida pullarni legallashtirishga qarshi kurashishdagi davlatlar saʼy-harakatlarini xalqaro miqyosda muvofiqlashtirish zarurati tugʻiladi. Jahonda jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurash, sudlar tomonidan sodir etilgan jinoyatlar uchun odillik prinsipiga asosan jazo tayinlash, jinoyat qonunchiligini liberallashtirishga alohida ahamiyat berilmoqda, jumladan, jinoiy faoliyatdan olingan daromadlarni legallashtirish uchun javobgarlikni belgilash hamda unga imkon bergan sabab va sharoitlarning oldini olish, ushbu jinoyatni toʻgʻri kvalifikatsiya qilish hamda uni sodir etganlik uchun javobgarlikni takomillashtirish, bu boradagi xalqaro standartlarning milliy qonunchilikka implementatsiyasini kuchaytirish sohasida tadqiqotlar oʻtkazishga alohida ahamiyat berilmoqda.

Kalit soʻzlar: jinoyat, jinoiy javobgarlik, jinoiy daromadlar, pul yuvish, legallashtirish, jazo.

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье анализируется общее понятие отмывания денег. Во всем мире международным сообществом, в том числе Организацией Объединенных Наций легализация доходов, полученных от преступной деятельности, признается одним из самых распространенных и опасных транснациональных преступлений. Нарастающая в современном мире общественная опасность легализации преступных доходов вызывает озабоченность подавляющего большинства стран мирового сообщества. По оценкам экспертов, в последние годы доходы от различного рода преступлений в сфере отмывания денег составляют от 2 до 5 % всего мирового валового продукта, то есть от 1 до 3 трлн долларов США. По мере глобализации мировой финансовой системы встает вопрос о необходимости координации усилий государств по противодействию отмыванию преступных доходов на международном уровне. В мире особое значение придается борьбе с преступностью, назначению судами наказаний за совершенные преступления согласно принципу справедливости, либерализации уголовного законодательства. Так, особое внимание уделяется проведению исследований в сфере определения ответственности за легализацию доходов, полученных от преступной деятельности, и предупреждению причин и условий, способствующих ее возникновению, правильной квалификации данного преступления, усилению имплементации в национальное законодательство международных стандартов в этой области.

Ключевые слова: преступление, уголовная ответственность, преступные доходы, отмывание денег, легализация, наказание

Introduction

Money laundering has become a growing concern for various organizations and governments globally in recent years due to its increasing prevalence. The scope of money laundering has expanded beyond national borders and has become a universal problem that affects individuals, states, and countries. This criminal activity poses challenges that are beyond the jurisdiction of any single state or country, and therefore requires international cooperation to combat. As a result, attention has been directed towards developing strategies and measures to prevent and detect money laundering, as well as investigating the legal implications and consequences of this crime.

Money laundering is often carried out through electronic means, such as depositing illegal funds in banks anonymously. This criminal activity is just one facet of a larger issue of criminal behavior. Money laundering involves utilizing illegally obtained funds and channeling them through various financial activities, such as entrepreneurship, transfer, and management. By transforming dirty money into legitimate business assets, criminals are able to hide the true origin of the funds and avoid detection. This process can be carried out electronically through banks, making it easier for criminals to conceal their identity and avoid scrutiny. As a result, there is a growing need to strengthen laws and regulations to prevent and detect money laundering activities and hold those responsible accountable for their actions.

The origin of money laundering dates back to the 1920s in the United States when criminal organizations, such as the American mafia, generated revenue through illegal activities such as robbery, prostitution, gambling, and drug trafficking. One of their strategies was to purchase legitimate businesses and combine the illegal funds generated by their criminal activities with legally obtained profits from these businesses. This enabled them to launder their illicit funds and disguise their true source of income. One of the most popular businesses used for money laundering was the laundry business, particularly laundromats, which were prevalent at the time. Criminal organizations invested heavily in this industry, allowing them to conceal their illegal activities and portray themselves as legitimate business owners. Money laundering involves concealing or disguising the proceeds of criminal activity as legitimate assets or income. As such, it remains a significant threat to the global economy, and efforts to combat it continue to evolve through legal and regulatory measures.

Materials and methods

General scientific methods such as historical, comparative legal, and logical (analysis and synthesis) methods were used in the framework of the article.

Research results

“Vienna Convention gives course of action for implementation of the framework for preventing money laundering, through law enforcement and control bodies. The regulatory nature of anti money laundry laws aim to immobilize the criminals. This involves identifying, arresting, and imprisoning the criminals. The regulatory nature of the anti money laundry is based upon voluntary compliance or punishment” [1]

A new contribution to countering the legalization of criminal proceeds was made by two UN Conventions: on November 15, 2000, the UN Convention against Transnational Organized Crime [2] was adopted, and on October 31, 2003, the UN Convention against Corruption [3].

The Financial Action Task Force on Money Laundering (FATF), which is recognized as the international standard setter for anti-money laundering efforts, defines the term “money laundering” succinctly as “the processing of...criminal proceeds to disguise their illegal origin” in order to “legitimize” the ill-gotten gains of crime [4].

In legal science, there are ideas that the "laundering" of revenue is inherent in an integral feature – the goal is to create the appearance of legality of obviously criminal income [5, p.100]

In modern history, the term "money laundering" was first used in the late twentieth century in the United States of America in relation to the proceeds of drug trafficking [6]

Taking into account these facts, all this leads to the transformation of legalization into a highly profitable and effective criminal production [7, p.6]

In the past, money laundering was primarily associated with serious crimes such as drug trafficking. However, today it is commonly recognized as an integral part of larger criminal activities. In certain countries, money laundering is also linked to corruption due to the complex financial transactions involved in the transfer of illicit funds. These transactions are intentionally designed to obscure the origin of the funds, making it difficult to trace them back to their illegal source. Money laundering experts utilize this complexity to successfully carry out the process of cleaning illicit funds. As a result, there is a growing need for more stringent measures and international cooperation to combat the proliferation of money laundering activities and hold those responsible accountable for their actions.

The monetary system in Uzbekistan operates under a free foreign exchange system, allowing for unrestricted transactions within the domestic banking system. As money laundering is typically linked to criminal activities, addressing this practice is crucial in combating organized crime, including corruption, bribery, smuggling, human trafficking, arms trade, terrorism, theft, embezzlement, fraud, forgery, gambling, prostitution, taxation, forestry, and environmental crimes. It is important to note that the nature and extent of money laundering in Uzbekistan may vary from other regions, and the types of criminal activities associated with it may change over time. Therefore, it is essential to continuously review and adapt anti-money laundering measures to effectively combat this criminal activity.

In the current challenging era, people are increasingly pushing their thinking to be more innovative. The concept of rewards has evolved from its original meaning. Previously, rewards for positive interactions were given without any favoritism or group interests, but now there are various symbols associated with human prestige for socially justifiable reasons.

In contemporary times, the concept of a "gift" often refers to a present given with the intent to influence a decision, and is typically controlled by the recipient's position-specific authority. However, not all individuals hold the belief that gifts are given with ulterior motives. One unresolved issue in Uzbekistan is the problem of money laundering, a crime that is frequently mentioned in the media using terms such as "money laundering," "cleaning money," "laundering money," or "illegal (dirty) transactions." Generally speaking, "money laundering" refers to the act of transforming an individual's assets derived from non-criminal activities into legitimate funds through various means. This practice enables the concealment of the assets' true origins.

The Ministry of Justice of Uzbekistan has registered an order from the Director of the Anti-Corruption Agency establishing the procedure for giving and receiving gifts by government officials during official trips and international events.

According to the document, government officials are prohibited from receiving gifts in exchange for the performance or non-performance of their duties in the interests of individuals or legal entities. However, gifts for special merits based on the decision of a government agency, as well as gifts for achievements in competitions, during state holidays, festive dates, and other official events, are not included in this ban.

Government officials may accept gifts during trips abroad, international and other official events, including within Uzbekistan. In this case, gifts must comply with the requirements of Uzbekistan's legislation and the internal departmental documents of the government agency, and must be voluntarily provided for a specific international or official event. Gifts should not lead to conflicts of interest or corruption risks, in particular, they should not create obligations that affect impartial decision-making.

Gifts should be accepted openly and transparently, without causing damage to the reputation of the government agency. Government officials should not demand or request gifts during official trips or international events.

Government officials may request documents from the donor confirming the value of their gift (cash or goods receipts, or other documents).

Flowers, food (pastries, etc.), office supplies from organizations (calendars, brochures, pens, and notebooks) given to government officials are not considered gifts and do not require registration.

Within three working days after returning from a business trip, the employee must submit a report on the receipt of the gift to the internal control structure of the government agency to combat corruption. If there is no receipt or invoice, the value of the gift is determined through internal or external expertise, including market value determined through trade points, the internet, and other sources.

If the value of the gift is less than 4 times the basic calculation value (1.2 million soums), then it remains the property of the employee (although the project provided for a sum of 5 times the basic calculation value). If the value exceeds 4 times the basic calculation value, then it is transferred to the balance of the government agency and can be used for the needs of the government agency.

In accordance with the Law on State Civil Service that came into force on November 10, 2022, the establishment of procedures for the receipt and delivery of gifts to civil servants is one of the measures aimed at preventing corruption in the field of state civil service. Other measures include preventing corrupt acts by civil servants, ensuring compliance with ethical standards of conduct, creating organizational and legal frameworks for preventing and resolving conflicts of interest among civil servants, implementing a system of income and asset declarations, and providing social protection, material support, and incentives for civil servants [8, p.19].

These measures also relate to combating money laundering.

The process of cleaning up white-collar crimes, which are fraudulent decisions made by individuals in positions of authority who hold and influence both government and private finances, is ongoing in Uzbekistan. Money laundering typically follows all financial crimes, which is why mandatory anti-money laundering laws are linked to various white-collar crime issues such as corruption, banking crimes, and illegal activities. In recent years, efforts have been made to enforce regulations for preventing money laundering.

It is therefore crucial to prevent criminals from benefiting from the consequences of their crimes. A transaction reporting system is in place for reporting money laundering crimes. It should be noted that the nature and scope of money laundering in Uzbekistan may differ from that of other regions, and the evolving landscape of crime requires continuous reevaluation and adaptation of anti-money laundering measures to effectively combat this illegal practice.

Confiscation of assets and properties is a common practice in Uzbekistan for those convicted of crimes. However, there are still numerous issues related to money laundering, particularly in terms of the laws and regulations used by law enforcement to identify and prosecute money laundering offenders, as well as challenges related to employment, law enforcement, and cultural norms within the community. These legal limitations, ambiguities, and contradictions pertain not only to substantive regulations but also to procedural regulations. Unfortunately, the enforcement of money laundering laws in Uzbekistan often fails to strike a fair balance between the rights of the accused and the interests of society as a whole. There have been cases where an individual who unknowingly received gifts or rewards obtained through money laundering has been wrongly implicated in the crime. The key factor is whether the individual was aware of the source of the proceeds of the crime. If they were not, they may still be subject to punishment for their involvement.

According to the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, money laundering refers to giving a legitimate appearance to property (money or other assets) obtained from criminal activity through its transfer, conversion, or exchange, as well as concealing or withholding the true nature, source, location, method of disposal, movement, or legitimate rights related to the money or other assets or their ownership, if they were obtained through criminal activity.

Nowadays, it's common for individuals to utilize electronic media on occasion, however, it's not uncommon for electronic and mass media to be abused, with one such example being money laundering. The objectives of money laundering crimes can take the form of being either intentional or a natural consequence.

In compliance with Uzbekistan's legal regulations, we do not utilize profits obtained directly. Money laundering can be categorized into three forms:

Active Money Laundering:

This pertains to an act committed by an individual who places, transfers, issues, converts, or exchanges money or securities derived from money laundering, with the intention to conceal the origin of the assets [9].

Passive Money Laundering:

This type of crime is directed towards individuals who receive or control the profits acquired from money laundering [10].

In accordance with the laws of Uzbekistan, there are three stages of money laundering:

Placement refers to the initial stage of transferring illicit funds obtained from criminal activities. This can be accomplished by physically moving cash in small increments, depositing it into the banking system, or smuggling it across borders [11].

Layering is the process of obscuring the origin of illicit funds by creating a complex web of financial transactions, effectively eliminating the traces of the money trail and creating anonymity.

Integration involves taking the proceeds of crime and passing them through the placement and layering stages to create an investment that appears to be legitimate. During this phase, the funds or assets are integrated into the existing financial system and are considered equal to other assets in the financial system.

The act of monetary settlement is a way to conceal or obfuscate the profits gained from a predicate offense to prevent it from being traced and used as evidence later on. This is why a wide range of financial crimes, such as white-collar crimes, are often monetized to conceal the illicit gains and avoid legal repercussions. To put it simply, monetary settlement is a method used to avoid accountability for financial crimes.

According to Article 243 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the maximum penalty for money laundering is 10 years of imprisonment.

The investigation focuses not only on the financial impact but also on the non-financial impact. As protecting the public's interests is a fundamental national ethical principle, the criminalization of money laundering is a necessary concept that should apply to business actors.

The application and criminal liability of money laundering vary across different laws, leading to discrepancies in their enforcement. These disparities can arise from various factors, such as laws that mention money laundering only as a subject matter without elaborating on the associated criminal penalties. Similarly, some laws regulate the criminal penalties but do not specify the representation of money laundering in criminal proceedings. Consequently, it becomes challenging to establish a standardized approach to prosecuting money laundering offenses. To ensure consistency in the application of criminal liability for money laundering, there is a need for harmonization of laws that regulate money laundering and the associated penalties. This can involve streamlining the criminal proceedings and penalties for all offenses related to money laundering. Such measures can help to strengthen the effectiveness of anti-money laundering efforts, thus preventing financial crimes and protecting the integrity of the financial system.

The existence of differences in the application and criminal liability of money laundering according to various laws that regulate this criminal act can result in uncertainty and inconsistencies in the legal system. Such disparities can be observed in various aspects, including laws that only mention money laundering as a subject without further elaboration on criminal penalties, or laws that regulate criminal penalties without addressing the representation of money laundering in criminal proceedings. This uncertainty can be particularly concerning when it comes to determining the position of money laundering as a criminal act and the legal consequences that apply to money launderers and their accomplices.

Moreover, the lack of uniformity in the definition, application, and criminal liability of money laundering can also contribute to the difficulties in identifying, prosecuting, and penalizing those involved in this criminal activity. As such, it is essential to establish clear and consistent legal frameworks and guidelines that address all aspects of money laundering, including its definition, legal consequences, and the roles and responsibilities of various actors involved in combating this illicit activity.

In addition, the complex nature of money laundering, as well as its potential to facilitate and fund various other criminal activities, makes it imperative to adopt a comprehensive and coordinated approach in tackling this issue. Such an approach should involve a range of measures, including enhanced international cooperation, strengthened regulatory frameworks, and increased awareness and education among relevant stakeholders, including financial institutions, law enforcement agencies, and the general public.

Overall, the disparities in the application and criminal liability of money laundering according to different laws and jurisdictions can have significant implications for the effectiveness of efforts to combat this crime. Therefore, it is crucial to work towards establishing clear and consistent legal frameworks that provide a robust and coordinated response to money laundering and related criminal activities.

In Uzbekistan, regulations require to report financial transactions involving assets suspected of being derived from criminal activity. Furthermore, suspicious financial transactions can be identified through various general indicators, such as a lack of clear economic or business purpose, the use of significant amounts of cash and/or abnormal criteria, and customer trading activities that deviate from the norm and appear unreasonable.

Financial transactions are crucial in every business activity, and it is essential to conduct checks to prevent money laundering. Criminals who engage in money laundering typically do not use the proceeds of their crimes immediately; instead, they try to obscure the origin of the funds to make them appear legitimate. Furthermore, they may use their illicit funds safely to finance their activities. Therefore, it is important to report any suspicious financial transactions to prevent or combat criminal spending and fundraising. However, not all financial transactions are criminal activities. Legitimate transactions, such as selling assets, are considered private commitments and should not be reported. However, financial service providers should report transactions that are suspicious, such as those with no clear economic or business purpose, large cash transactions, or transactions outside the norm. In Uzbekistan, reporting these types of transactions is required by law.

There can be issues with financial transactions, such as when the recipient receives a gift from a family member that exceeds its value or when the provider has an agency relationship with the recipient. Before considering such transactions as money laundering, it is important to understand whether they violate established rules. If so, the recipient should refuse or report the transaction to the appropriate authorities. In addition, if the grant is an important decision for the donor, the recipient should be able to decline or report it. Otherwise, if the recipient is receiving a gift from the same provider, they should consider whether it is necessary to report it.

Criminal proceeds are assets obtained from criminal activities, such as corruption, which is punishable by law in Uzbekistan. It is crucial to prevent criminals from benefiting from their crimes and to report any suspicious financial transactions to the authorities to combat money laundering.

Money laundering can have a significant negative impact on the nation and its surrounding community, particularly when committed by members of the community. Such offenses can be detrimental to the economy and should be prevented according to the laws of Uzbekistan.

Embezzlement can be defined as a deliberate act of controlling an object or item that is the result of a criminal offense, whether fully or partially. However, receiving a gift from someone does not necessarily mean that the gift is a result of embezzlement. Embezzlement is considered as an act of deviation that abuses the trust given by others to the person in possession of the goods. There are no specific criteria to identify money from money laundering crimes, but authorities may recognize the characteristics of individuals who receive the proceeds of such crimes through unusual financial growth or changes in their financial records. However, these criteria are not a definite indication that someone has received money from money laundering crimes, and the police must carry out several stages of investigation to capture individuals who have committed money laundering crimes in accordance with the laws of Uzbekistan.

Conclusions

Money laundering through gift-giving can be accomplished in several ways. Here are some of them:

1. Gifts in exchange for services: One way to launder money may be to give a gift in exchange for services. For example, if a company receives money from a counterparty into its bank account, it can transfer part of these funds to the counterparty's bank account as payment for services, and then give them a gift exceeding the payment for the services.

2. Gifts to family and friends: One way to launder money may be to give gifts to close relatives or friends. For example, a person may give money to their family or friends as a gift for a birthday or other holiday. These funds may be obtained from dishonest or illegal sources but will appear as clean money that can be used freely.

3. Charitable gifts: Another way to launder money may be through charitable gifts. For example, a person may donate a large sum of money to a charitable organization that can use these funds for its purposes, and then receive back some or all of this money through gifts that the charitable organization may give in return.

4. Gifts in exchange for purchases: One way to launder money may be to buy goods from a company and then receive a gift that exceeds the purchase price. For example, a person may buy a car and receive a gift in return, such as a vacation at an expensive resort, which exceeds the cost of the car.

5. Gifts in exchange for investments: One way to launder money may be to give money as an investment and then receive the funds back in the form of gifts. For example, a person may give money as an investment in a certain company, and then receive in return a gift that exceeds the amount of the investment.

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